

PHYTOCHEMICAL, ANTIBACTERIAL AND ANTIFUNGAL ANALYSES OF *MORINGA OLEIFERA* AGAINST SELECTED FUNGAL AND BACTERIAL PATHOGENS.

*¹Bello, H. O., ¹Jimoh H. M. and ²Moro, D. D.

¹Department of Science Laboratory Technology, Ogun State Institute of Technology, P.M. B. 2005, Igbesa, Ogun State, Nigeria.

²Department of Microbiology, Lagos State University, P. M. B. 001, Ojo, Lagos, Lagos State, Nigeria

Corresponding Email: bello.hakeem25@gmail.com

Corresponding Phone Number: +234-8034539671

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Abstract: This study investigated the phyto-chemical composition and antimicrobial properties of *Moringa oleifera* leaf extracts against selected bacterial and fungal pathogens. Specifically, the antibacterial activity was tested against *Klebsiella* spp., *Citrobacter braakii*, and *Enterobacter aerogenes*, while the antifungal activity was assessed against *Aspergillus niger* and *Rhodotorula* spp. Phytochemical screening of both aqueous and ethanolic extracts revealed the presence of alkaloids and saponins in both, while terpenoids, cardiac glycosides, and quinones were detected only in the ethanolic extract. Antimicrobial activity was evaluated using the agar well diffusion method. The results showed that the ethanolic extract exhibited greater antimicrobial activity than the aqueous extract, with *Klebsiella* spp. showing the highest sensitivity (zone of inhibition up to 16 mm), followed by *Citrobacter braakii* and *Enterobacter aerogenes*. For fungal pathogens, the ethanolic extract showed moderate inhibition against *Rhodotorula* spp. (up to 12 mm) and lower activity against *Aspergillus niger* (maximum of 8 mm). Aqueous extracts demonstrated comparatively lower efficacy. The study concludes that *Moringa oleifera* contains phyto-chemicals with significant antibacterial and moderate antifungal properties, particularly in ethanol-based extractions. These findings support the potential use of *Moringa oleifera* as a natural antimicrobial agent, especially in managing infections caused by drug-resistant pathogens. Further studies involving compound isolation and *in vivo* validation are recommended.

INTRODUCTION

Moringa oleifera, a fast-growing, drought-resistant plant native to South Asia and widely cultivated across Africa, is recognised for its nutritional and medicinal properties. Various parts of the plant, especially the leaves and seeds,

contain a wide array of phyto-chemicals such as flavonoids, alkaloids, tannins, saponins, and phenolic compounds, which have been documented to exhibit antimicrobial, antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, and anticancer activities (Rahman *et al.*, 2020; Nadeem *et al.*,

2021). These bio-active constituents make *Moringa oleifera* a promising candidate in the development of plant-based antimicrobial formulations. There has been growing recognition of the importance of anti-oxidants and essential trace elements in human nutrition, as a result of their vital role in maintaining health and preventing chronic diseases (Rizvi *et al.*, 2014; Cannas *et al.*, 2020).

The emergence of bacterial pathogens such as *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, *Citrobacter braakii*, and *Enterobacter aerogenes*, all belonging to the Enterobacteriaceae family, is of particular concern due to their intrinsic resistance and ability to acquire resistance genes. These bacteria are often implicated in nosocomial infections, including urinary tract infections, bloodstream infections, and pneumonia (Tadesse *et al.*, 2023).

Citrobacter braakii is a less commonly reported but increasingly recognized species within the *Citrobacter* genus. It is a Gram-negative, facultatively anaerobic rod that is part of the normal gut microbiota in humans and animals but can act as an opportunistic pathogen under certain conditions (Sundararajan *et al.*, 2021).

Klebsiella spp. are Gram-negative, non-motile, encapsulated bacilli that belong to the family Enterobacteriaceae. Among the species, *Klebsiella pneumoniae* is the most clinically significant, known to cause pneumonia, urinary tract infections (UTIs), septicemia, and wound infections, particularly in hospitalised and immuno-compromised individuals (Kang *et al.*, 2022).

Similarly, fungal pathogens such as *Aspergillus niger* and *Rhodotorula spp.* are increasingly

associated with opportunistic infections in immune-compromised individuals, with growing resistance to standard antifungal agents. The major classes of phyto-chemicals include alkaloids, flavonoids, tannins, saponins, phenols, glycosides, terpenoids, and steroids, each with distinct biochemical mechanisms. Alkaloids, for example, have been reported to interfere with DNA replication and enzyme activity in microbial cells, while flavonoids exhibit antimicrobial effects by disrupting microbial membranes and inhibiting nucleic acid synthesis (Rahman *et al.*, 2020).

The antibacterial action of *Moringa oleifera* is primarily attributed to the disruption of bacterial cell walls and membranes by its bioactive constituents. Flavonoids and phenolic acids, for instance, are known to interfere with bacterial enzyme systems and nucleic acid synthesis, leading to microbial death (Nadeem *et al.*, 2021). Saponins contribute to antibacterial activity by increasing membrane permeability, while tannins can precipitate bacterial proteins and inhibit cell adhesion (Rahman *et al.*, 2020).

Fungal infections are increasingly becoming a global health concern, especially among immuno-compromised individuals. Opportunistic fungi such as *Aspergillus niger* and *Rhodotorula spp.* are capable of causing systemic infections with high morbidity and mortality rates. The limitations associated with current antifungal agents such as toxicity, high cost, and increasing resistance have prompted the search for alternative therapies, particularly those derived from medicinal plants like *Moringa oleifera* (Mahto *et al.*, 2021; Lim *et al.*, 2022;). The aim of this study is to investigate the

various phyto-chemicals and the antimicrobial activity of extracts of *Moringa oleifera* against selected bacterial and fungal pathogens in Igbesa, Ogun State, Nigeria.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Collection and Preparation of Plant Material

Fresh Moringa leaves were obtained from a local market in Lusada, Igbesa and Ogun State. The leaves were washed thoroughly with clean water to remove dirt and debris, then air-dried at room temperature for 7–10 days in a shaded area to prevent degradation of phyto-chemicals by sunlight. The dried leaves were ground into fine powder using an electric blender and stored in airtight containers until extraction.

Quality assurance of tignuts

During the research, appropriate quality assurance precautions and procedures were followed as the field and laboratory methods were adjusted to ensure data quality. As a result, sample bottles were thoroughly cleaned with hydrochloric acid and they were then rinsed in the laboratory with de-ionised water. All the reagents were analytical grade and the glasswares were properly cleaned. The tignuts were obtained within Igbesa town. All laboratory tests for the quality of the tignuts were performed according to standard methods using AAS (Model). De-ionised water was used throughout the study. Samples for trace elements were collected within Igbesa town and examined independently in the laboratory.

Preparation of Extracts

Aqueous extract: About 100g of Moringa leaves were dissolved in 400 mL of distilled water for 2 h.

Methanol Extract: About 100g of Moringa leaves were dissolved in 400 mL of methanol for 2 h.

Quantitative Phytochemical Screening

1. Test for alkaloids

Two mL of the sample was mixed with 2 mL of concentrated hydrochloric acid. Few drops of Mayer's reagent later added to the mixture. The development of a green coloration in the sample suggested the presence of alkaloids.

2. Tests for tannins

To 1 mL of the sample in a tube, 2 mL of freshly made ferric chloride (5%) were added. The development of a greenish-black colour suggested that tannins were present in the sample.

3. Test for Phenols

One mL of the sample was mixed with 2 mL of distilled water. 10% ferric chloride was then gradually added to the mixture. The development of a green colour suggested that the sample contained phenols.

4. Test for Oxalate

To 2 mL of each liquid samples in a test tube, a few drops of glacial acetic acid were added. The formation of greenish-black coloration indicated the presence of oxalates.

5. Test for saponins

Two mL each of the sample and distilled water were placed into a tube, then shaken lengthwise for 15 minutes. 1 cm layer of foam formed, indicated the presence of saponins in the sample.

6. Test for Terpenoids

Before adding concentrated sulphuric acid, 2 mL of chloroform were applied to 500 μ L of sample. The emergence of a reddish-brown

colour in the sample suggested the presence of terpenoids.

7. Test for Cardiac glycosides

The sample was diluted to 500 L with glacial acetic acid (2 mL) and a few drops of ferric chloride (5%) solution. To the mixture, 1 mL of concentrated sulfuric acid was added. The development of a brown ring at the interface suggested the presence of cardiac glycosides in the sample.

8. Test for quinones

To 1 mL of material, 1 mL of pure sulfuric acid was added. The development of a red color served as signs that quinones were present in the sample.

Test Microorganisms

The bacteria tested included *Citrobacter braakii*, *Enterobacter aerogenes* and *Klebsiella* spp. while the fungi were *Aspergillus niger* and *Rhodotorula* spp.

All isolates were obtained from Crawford University laboratory, confirmed by standard microbiological and biochemical tests, and maintained on appropriate agar slants.

Antibacterial and Antifungal Assay

Preparation of Inoculum

The bacterial isolates were grown on nutrient agar and adjusted to 0.5 McFarland standard ($\sim 1.5 \times 10^8$ CFU/ml) and fungal isolates were grown on potato dextrose agar (PDA) and adjusted to $\sim 10^6$ spores/ml.

Agar Well Diffusion Method

Sterile Mueller-Hinton agar (for bacteria) and Sabouraud dextrose agar (for fungi) were poured into Petri dishes. About 0.1 ml of each

standardised inoculum was evenly spread on the surface. Wells (6 mm) were bored using a sterile cork-borer.

About 100 μ l of each extract (concentration range: 100, 200, 300 mg/ml) was introduced into the wells.

The positive control were standard antibiotics/antifungals (e.g., ciprofloxacin, fluconazole), while the **negative control** was solvent only (distilled water or methanol)

Plates were incubated as follows: The bacteria plates were incubated for 24 hours at 37°C and fungal plates were incubated for 72 hours at 28–30°C

Measurement of Zones of Inhibition

After incubation, clear zones around the wells were measured in millimeters (mm). Larger zones indicate higher antimicrobial activity. The zone diameter breakpoints used are based on CLSI (Clinical and Laboratory Standards Institute) guidelines as followed:

Sensitive (S) ≥ 21 mm,

Intermediate (I) 16–20 mm

Resistant (R) ≤ 15 mm

RESULTS

A very high presence of alkaloids and saponins, but absence of tannins, phenols, oxalates, terpenoids, cardiac glycosides and quinones were observed in the aqueous extract. However, a very high presence of alkaloids. A moderate presence of terpenoids and cardiac glycosides, with the absence of all antimicrobial compounds was found in the ethanoic extract (Table 1).

TABLE 1: Phytochemical Analysis of the Moringa Leave Extract

	Alkaloids	Tannins	Phenols	Oxalates	Saponins	Terpenoids	Cardiac glycosides	Quinones
ML aq	++	-	-	-	++	-	-	-
ML e	++	-	-	-	+	+	+	-

KEY:

++ (Detected)

+ (moderately detected)

- (not detected)

ML aq: Aqueous extract of Moringa leaves

ML e: Ethanol extract of Moringa leaves

Table 2 shows that the ethanolic extract had more antibacterial activities against the three bacteria as concentration increases with more effect on *Klebsiella* spp., *Citrobacter braakii* and the least activity against *Enterobacter aerogenes*.

Table 2: Ethanol Extract of the Sample on Bacteria

S/N	CONCENTRATION	<i>Citrobacter braakii</i>	<i>Enterobacter aerogenes</i>	<i>Klebsiella</i> spp.
1.	0.2	10mm	7mm	10mm
2.	0.3	12mm	8mm	14mm
3.	0.4	16mm	11mm	15mm

The aqueous extract of Moringa leaves also showed antimicrobial activity against the bacterial isolates with increasing concentrations.

Table 3 shows that the aqueous extract of the sample on bacteria. And *Klebsiella* spp. had the

highest susceptibility, followed by *Enterobacter aerogenes* and *Citrobacter braakii* with the least at varying concentrations.

Table 3: Antibacterial activity of aqueous leaves extract of Moringa

S/N	CONCENTRATION	<i>Citrobacter braakii</i>	<i>Enterobacter aerogenes</i>	<i>Klebsiella</i> spp.
1.	0.2	6mm	7mm	12mm
2.	0.3	8mm	8mm	14mm
3.	0.4	12mm	10mm	16mm

Findings from antifungal effect of the ethanolic extract also increases with concentrations. At 0.2 mL, the extract inhibited *Rhodotorula* spp., but

no effect on the *A. niger*. With the concentrations of 0.3 and 0.4 mL, both fungi were susceptible as the concentrations increased (Table 4).

Table 4: Ethanolic extract of the sample on fungi

S/N	CONCENTRATION	<i>Aspergillus niger</i>	<i>Rhodotorula</i> spp.
1.	0.2	0mm	4mm
2.	0.3	6mm	10mm
3.	0.4	8mm	12mm

From Table 5, it was found that none of the fungi was susceptible the aqueous extract with concentration of 0.3 mL, at 0.3 mL concentration, *A. niger* was not susceptible, but *Rhodotorula* was susceptible. Some degree of

antifungal susceptibility was demonstrated by aqueous extract against *A. niger*, but a relatively higher susceptibility was shown against *Rhodotorula* spp. At 0.4 mL concentration of the extract.

Table 5: Aqueous extract of the sample on fungi

S/N	CONCENTRATION	<i>Aspergillus niger</i>	<i>Rhodotorula</i> spp.
1.	0.2	0mm	0mm
2.	0.3	0mm	8mm
3.	0.4	4mm	10mm

DISCUSSION

The data obtained from this study provide clear evidence that *Moringa oleifera* leaf extracts possess considerable antimicrobial properties, especially when extracted with ethanol. The phyto-chemical screening revealed that both aqueous and ethanol extracts contained important bioactive compounds such as alkaloids and saponins, while terpenoids, cardiac glycosides, and quinones were detected only in the ethanol extract. This chemical profile is critical to understanding the antimicrobial potential of *Moringa oleifera*

In the antibacterial assays, the ethanolic extract consistently exhibited higher zones of inhibition

across all tested bacterial species compared to the aqueous extract. Among the test organisms, *Klebsiella* spp. showed the highest sensitivity to both extract types, followed by *Citrobacter braakii* and *Enterobacter aerogenes*. This suggests that the antibacterial effect of *Moringa oleifera* is species-dependent and concentration-specific. For example, at 0.4 mg/ml, the ethanolic extract produced a 16 mm zone of inhibition against *Klebsiella* spp., whereas the same concentration of the aqueous extract yielded only 10 mm. These findings align with previous research emphasizing that ethanol extracts are generally more effective in solubilising and delivering antimicrobial

phytochemicals (Rahman *et al.*, 2020; Hamzah *et al.*, 2023). *Enterobacter aerogenes* is a motile, Gram-negative bacterium from the *Enterobacteriaceae* family, and is commonly associated with nosocomial infections such as pneumonia, septicemia, UTIs, and wound infections. Like other hospital-acquired pathogens, *E. aerogenes* is notorious for its capacity to develop resistance to multiple antibiotics, including carbapenems and third-generation cephalosporins (Kotsanas *et al.*, 2020).

It is quite interesting to note from this study that both aqueous and ethanolic extract were more active against bacterial than fungi. This might have to do with the differences in the components of bacterial and fungal cell walls (Lim *et al.*, 2022).

The antifungal results showed that the ethanol extract was moderately effective against *Rhodotorula* spp., producing a maximum inhibition zone of 12 mm at higher concentrations, while its activity against *Aspergillus niger* was relatively low, with a maximum of 8 mm. In contrast, the aqueous extract demonstrated poor antifungal activity overall, with minimal or no inhibition, especially at lower concentrations. This suggests that fungal pathogens like *Aspergillus niger* may possess more robust cellular defences or structural features that make them less susceptible to the phyto-chemicals in *Moringa oleifera* (Lim *et al.*, 2022).

The antifungal activity of the compounds appear to be associated with alkaloids and saponins as all leaf extracts with both chemical compound showed very high antifungal activity than all

other compounds recovered from *Moringa oleifera* leaves. These leaves have been associated with biological activities, including hypo-cholesterolemic, anti-diabetic and hypertensive agents, regulates thyroid, central nervous system, digestive system, genito-urinary system, and in the treatment of gastric ulcers and scurvy. Saponins can bind to cholesterol in microbial cell membranes, leading to pore formation and leakage of cellular contents, and tannins form irreversible complexes with microbial proteins, rendering them inactive (Hamzah *et al.*, 2023).. This further underscore its effect on microbial pathogens, with prospects as an important medicinal plant.

The results also confirm that antimicrobial activity increases with concentration, supporting a dose-dependent relationship. This trend was evident across both bacterial and fungal species and for both extracts, although more pronounced in ethanol-based treatments.

Conclusion: Both aqueous and ethanolic extracts of *Moringa oleifera* have both antibacterial and antifungal activities against the selected bacteria and fungi tested, so have prospects of being used in modern antimicrobial formulations, as earlier studies have reported a wide array of antimicrobial compounds like alkaloids, saponins, tannins, phenolic compounds etc. in tigernuts.

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